

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: AUSTRALIA

Caddisflies of the Otway Ranges, Victoria, Australia

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We are both curators at Museums Victoria in Melbourne. In mid 2018 we began an assessment of stream communities in the Otway Ranges, about 150-200 km south west of Melbourne, after this region had suffered from bushfires. We chose to concentrate on adult caddisflies as these are numerous and diverse in this region, but we also sampled adult mayflies and stoneflies (EPT taxa). These three orders are known to be sensitive to disturbances both man-made and natural and are thus obvious targets for any assessment of river conditions. Here we deal solely with the caddisflies.

The Otway Ranges is a region of high country (maximum

able; so knowledge of their natural colours and wing patterns was absent. From our high resolution images we will produce a photographic key to the adult caddisflies in the belief that an identification key will facilitate future environmental surveys by non-specialists such as staff from the national park. The Otway Ranges have been repeatedly burnt by wildfire and naturally one of the concerns of the national park authorities is to determine the extent of disturbance and the degree of recovery of invertebrate species, especially those in rivers which can be inundated with ash and sediment after fires.

Our main technique was high resolution digital macro photography. Adults were photographed during the day when they emerge onto rocks or vegetation along the banks. At night adults were attracted using UV lights. We have discovered that a UV light set up underneath a bridge provides excellent conditions for photography (Fig. 1). Adults usually will settle on the vertical walls underneath a bridge where they can be readily photographed. Thus our survey work was done both at night and during the day, but night work tended to produce the most species. After several photos had been taken of each specimen, the adult was captured using a pooter and preserved in 70% ethanol. This proved very productive and provided specimens at all sites examined. Preserved specimens were identified using existing keys under low magnification. Photos and specimens were registered in the museum's collection database.

A total of 2300 individual caddisflies, representing at least 63 species and 19 families, were individually photographed and collected at 36 sites, encompassing 17 creeks and rivers (Table 1). Most specimens were of described species.

Fig. 1 A typical sampling site in the Otway Ranges showing the river bed and the UV lights set up underneath a bridge.

elevation is about 600m) that lies adjacent to Bass Strait and stretches for about 120 km along the coast, which points in a south-west north-east direction. It is mostly covered in forest, which has been logged in the past, but today much of the region is included in the Great Otway National Park. Numerous rivers arise in these ranges with those in the southern part of the ranges generally flowing short distances (< 50km) before they reach the sea.

Between October 2018 and April 2021, we surveyed the caddisfly communities at many of these shorter rivers. Our aim was to assess caddisfly diversity by photographing, capturing and subsequently identifying live adult specimens. For many of these species, live photographs were not previously avail-

able. However, we found a small number of undescribed species. The range of families encountered was typical for forested catchments in Victoria and the number of species recorded represented about one third of those known from Victoria. The most diverse families (Leptoceridae, Hydrobiosidae, Conoesucidae, Philorheithridae) in the Otways are also diverse elsewhere in Australia. Photos of the adults (Fig. 2) show differences in colour, wing pattern, antennal length and size. These characteristics have enabled us to distinguish species and provide diagnostic features that will be incorporated into a key to the adults. Because of their high resolution our photos can be greatly enlarged. This is a distinct advantage when searching for critical characters on the adults.

Fig. 2 Caddisflies (Trichoptera) from the Great Otway National Park. Body length in mm. *Anisocentropus bicoloratus* (Calamoceratidae), female, NMV TRI55315, 10.3 mm (upper left); *Hampa patona* (Conoesucidae), male, NMV TRI55492, 6.6 mm (upper centre); *Apsilochorema gisburn* (Hydrobiosidae), male, NMV TRI55491, 8.2 mm (upper right); *Asmicridea edwardsi* (Hydropsychidae), male, NMV TRI55459, 8.5 mm (lower left); *Hydrobiosella gibbera* (Philopotamidae) (lower centre); *Tasimia palpata* (Tasimiidae), male, NMV TRI55431, 6.5 mm (lower right). The NMV codes are the registration numbers of the specimens.

At several of our sites we have samples from every month of the year. These data will enable us to investigate the timing of emergence and the length of the life cycles of the caddisfly species. Such biological data may be invaluable in determining the effects of disturbances on this fauna. We also have photos of adult mayflies and stoneflies of the Otways. There appear to be fewer photographic features for these taxa that are useful for distinguishing species, but this opinion may change with further work.

Bushfires appear to have had little long-lasting effect on the diversity of EPT taxa in the Otway Ranges. However, we have yet to examine compositional differences between sites with different fire histories. We hope that producing a photographic key to the adult caddisflies will enable such assessments to be made in the future with greater ease.

Details of our initial work on this project during the 2018-2019 Otway Bioscan, including a short video describing our techniques, [can be viewed here](#).

The final report arising from the Otway Bioscan, including additional information and images of all EPT taxa sampled, [can be downloaded here](#).

<https://museumsvictoria.com.au/>

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Table 1. Caddisflies collected in the Great Otway National Park from October 2018 to April 2021. The number of species collected, and the number of rivers where each family was encountered are shown. A total of 17 rivers were sampled.

Family	No. of species	No. of rivers
Atriplectidae	1	10
Calamoceratidae	2	6
Calocidae	2	5
Conoesucidae	6	10
Enomidae	5	9
Glossomatidae	2	7
Helicophidae	1	3
Helicopsychidae	2	5
Hydrobiosidae	9	12
Hydropsychidae	2	9
Hydroptilidae	>1	5
Kokiriidae	1	1
Leptoceridae	16	13
Limnephilidae	1	3
Odontoceridae	1	3
Philopotamidae	2	6
Philorheithridae	6	9
Polycentropodidae	2	8
Tasimiidae	2	5